

Philippines Insurgency

The Philippines government has been dealing with insurgency for over a decade. The conflict caused by some militant-rebel groups is gaining too much attention from the international communities, particularly the human rights groups and the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees, so various studies and researches have been conducted and are being conducted by some scholars and peace advocates to assist the government and the rebel arm groups in reaching an agreement that will satisfy the demands and requirements set by both parties.

Many rebel groups have emerged from various sectors, ethnicities, and cultures. Each faction fights for what they believe to be right. Oppression, discrimination, and inequity in economic distribution are just a few of the major reasons why they are revolting against the government.

As a student and professional who grew up in a conflict zone between a certain group and the Government of the Republic of the Philippines (GRP), I can tell you that this struggle and constant fighting can only lead to two outcomes: death and fierceness.

Too many people were killed as a result of the conflict. There were far too many resources squandered. Death of civilians, military personnel, and insurgents, as well as the economy. They are fearful that one of their loved ones will be forced to fight and join the groups.

International organizations are constantly extending their assistance to alleviate the deteriorating situation. They are, however, constrained and limited by the boundaries of what they can assist with. They must never be directly involved in any military conflict. They can only provide military training and exercises, such as the infamous Balikatan exercise between the United States and the Philippines, military equipment and facilities, intelligence reports, financial assistance to civilians, and initiating and facilitating peace talks.

These international community contributions are making a significant contribution to the reduction of insurgencies, such as the peace talks in Mindanao between the large rebel group and the GRP. Both parties agreed to a cease-fire and to continue talks to resolve the long-running conflict between group fighters and government troops. However, we must accept that you will not be able to satisfy all of the members and stakeholders with your performance. In short, there are those who do not agree and do not wish to resolve the conflict peacefully through dialogue, preferring instead to engage in an arm-to-arm confrontation. For a variety of reasons, such as losing family members while fighting their enemies, being brainwashed by radicals, or because of what they are getting from opposition politicians.

As a result, whatever and whoever initiates programs to assist both parties in resolving conflicts will be less successful if there is no full cooperation and control among all members.